

Application Citizen Science Hubs 2024

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Section 1 – General information

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Lay summary in English (50-100 words)

Title of the proposal	<i>The Hub for Impactful and Engaged Research (HIER)</i>
Author, Affiliation	<i>Chiara Stenico; Charlotte Bruns; Tanya Yankelevich; Margaret Gold</i>
Text	<i>The Hub for Impactful and Engaged Research (HIER) transforms the fragmented landscape of Civic Engagement (CE) by establishing a center of excellence across five connected knowledge institutions. Through a well-structured, transdisciplinary network, HIER will coordinate and showcase best CE practices, making them accessible to researchers, educators, professional services, and civic networks. Its impact is driven by three core focus areas: Institutional embedding, CE capacity-building, and collaboration liaising. HIER will implement institution-specific support, cross-collaborative initiatives, and knowledge-sharing events. HIER will advance Impactful and Engaged research to be 'hier' for citizens and communities to be included in systems of knowledge co-production.</i>

Lekensamenvatting (Lay summary in Dutch) (50-100 woorden)

Titel van de aanvraag	<i>De Hub for Impactful and Engaged Research (HIER)</i>
Author, Instelling	<i>Chiara Stenico; Charlotte Bruns; Tanya Yankelevich; Margaret Gold</i>
Nederlandse tekst	<i>De Hub for Impactful and Engaged Research (HIER) transformeert het versnipperde landschap van maatschappelijke betrokkenheid (CE) door een centrum van excellentie op te richten binnen vijf verbonden kennisinstellingen. Via een gestructureerd, transdisciplinair netwerk zal HIER CE-praktijken coördineren en zichtbaar maken, zodat ze toegankelijk zijn voor onderzoekers, docenten, professionele diensten en burgersnetwerken. De impact van HIER wordt gedreven door drie kerngebieden: institutionele verankering, capaciteitsopbouw en samenwerking. HIER implementeert instellingsspecifieke ondersteuning, cross-collaboratieve initiatieven en kennisdelingsevenementen. HIER bevordert impactvol en betrokken onderzoek, zodat het 'hier' is voor burgers en gemeenschappen om deel te nemen aan kennisproductie.</i>

Section 2 – Description of the Citizen Science Hub

1. Team composition: quality of the team (criterion 1: 30%)

The **Hub for Impactful and Engaged Research (HIER)** joins Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR), Erasmus Medical Center (EMC), Delft University of Technology (TUD), Leiden University (LU), and Leiden University Medical Center (LUMC) in a collaboration to advance excellent **Civic Engagement (CE)** practices in the province of South Holland. CE encompasses a broad spectrum of participatory research approaches, ranging from Citizen Science (CS) and related methodologies with the potential to *actively* involve citizens and communities in research, such as Community-Based Participatory Research (CBPR), Participatory Democracy and Action Research (PAR), and Living Labs (LL), to Science Communication and broader Public Engagement (PE) initiatives. This hub leverages strategic regional programmes and each institution's complementary strengths to consolidate and innovate **institutional support capacity** for CE. From EUR's Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)-driven valorisation of scientific knowledge to TUD's technical and social innovation capacity, and LU's impact-oriented 'healthy living society' initiatives, alongside Erasmus MC and LUMC's public- and patient-participation in research traditions. Embedded in these institutional backgrounds, the partnering team pools diverse expertise within and across the institutes in a 'Hub and spoke' structure.

Starting with coordinating and research expertise in **Citizen Science and Community-Based Participatory research:** HIER hub coordinator and EUR spoke-site coordinator Chiara Stenico (0.8 FTE) centrally supports EUR researchers across faculties to identify expertise and networks to develop their CE initiatives and transdisciplinary collaborations and promotes institutional awareness around responsible CE practices; and Willem Scholten (0.1 FTE) coordinates and represents Open and Responsible Science in EUR's institutional strategy development on engaged and transdisciplinary research. TUD spoke-site coordinator Tanya Yankelevich (0.5 FTE) leads citizen science support and participatory methodology training while coordinating TUD university-wide CE strategy development efforts; and Marit Bogert (0.2 FTE) supports researchers with citizen science project implementation, co-creation, and resource co-creation with communities at the TUD Science Centre. LU spoke-site coordinator Margaret Gold (0.3 FTE) leads LU's university-wide CE efforts and the Citizen Science Lab research hub and project incubator, providing expertise in responsible research and innovation, impact assessment, and cross-disciplinary citizen science projects. The core team is further strengthened by CE research expertise brought in by Jurian Edelenbos (EUR, 0.05 FTE) who leads community-based research at Vital Cities and Citizens and WijkWijs. Team members from the medical centers, Amy van Grieken (Erasmus MC, 0.01 FTE) and Joost Oude Groeniger (Erasmus MC, 0.01 FTE), connect with local communities to improve public health through initiatives like academic workplace. Parallely, Sonja Meeuwssen (LUMC, 0.02 FTE) and Jessica Kieft-de Jong (LUMC, 0.02 FTE) focus on community health research and societal collaborations for a healthy society. Each HIER spoke-site is embedded within their respective University research support structures providing services such as research data stewardship, ethical, and legal advice, with whom spoke-site coordinators closely liaise. All five HIER partners have Open Science Programmes and all three universities have Open Science Communities through which knowledge and know-how can be further spread and amplified to staff in all domains, in which the core team are either community managers (OSCD) or close collaborators (OSCR, OSCL). HIER furthermore uniquely complements CS and CBPR expertise with **Science Communication and Public Engagement expertise:** Saskia Postema (TUD, 0.1 FTE) coordinates community engagement initiatives in WijkStad to connect societal challenges with educators and researchers who can support finding solutions and supports the creation of a neighbourhood university (Wijkuniversiteit), a center for community learning in Delft. Marit Bogert develops public educational programmes. Jelle Burger (TUD, 0.2 FTE) coordinates the WijkWijs programme and supports participatory projects with local communities in Rotterdam, as well as facilitates strategic partnerships across EUR and TUD. At EUR, Jason Pridmore (0.05 FTE) and his team collaborators, Charlotte Bruns and Simone Driessen, contribute through their research on trust in science and participatory methodologies. They also lead the EU-funded COALESCE competence center for science communication, bringing wider science communication expertise into HIER, next to LU's Science Communication and Society research center and Master's programme. Marieke van Haaren (0.3 FTE) brings city residents, students, and science together in community engaged learning in the 'Leren met de Stad' programme. This team's potential will be further amplified through dedicated (science) communication expertise, which includes advisory and training support, as well as practical assistance in showcasing impactful practices, coordinating HIER's content strategy, and managing events. This will enable the infrastructure that we now turn to describe.

2. Project plan (criterion 2: 40%)

Addressing a largely fragmented landscape of CE programmes and initiatives, too often leading to short-term efforts and missed CE opportunities in the region, HIER sets out to **coordinate** and **demonstrate** the ways in which the five universities support researchers and educators with CE efforts. HIER is envisioned to become a centre of excellence, creating a **well-structured and interconnected network** which coordinates excellent CE practices and makes these visible and accessible to researchers, professional services, civic networks and communities in the region. This approach will guide both experienced and novice researchers and educators (key hub users) to harness and align existing expertise and resources for impactful engaged research. It will also strengthen institutional recognition of their value by showcasing and demonstrating their impacts. HIER will additionally **foster innovative CE professional support services** by crossing engagement expertise and collaborating across a transdisciplinary network. By placing citizens and other societal actors at the core of all activities via user-centred, open, transparent, reciprocal, and reflexive research frameworks, HIER aims ultimately to enhance the transformative potential of scientific inquiry.

HIER's Workplan: To achieve this, the activities of the Hub are structured into three interconnected **focus areas** (FA). These are coordinated by the HIER team and spanning the partner's spoke-sites to balance internal activities that are tailored to the partner universities and their specific institutional structures, with transdisciplinary efforts that engage the participating medical centres and the broader HIER's network. All activities inform the complementary work of other focus areas through core **coordinating activities** of the HIER team, such as co-created agendas, the co-development of coordinating support materials, as well as through iterative reflection and active learning from the outcomes of all activities, allowing all universities to effectively collaborate to grow internal activities and transdisciplinary efforts at once. Iterative engagement with the **wider HIER network** will serve to continuously improve the focus areas, evolving dynamically through HIER collaborations with local, regional, as well as international developments and key enablers. The following outlines the foundational framework which will be further developed in **M24**.

FA1: Institutionally Promoting & Embedding CE practices. To more fully embed CE practices within the partner institutes, we will host yearly **intra- and inter- institutional dialogues** with university leadership, professional services staff, researchers and educators across the partnership, and civil society representatives (**FA1.1**). These events will raise awareness about the challenges and opportunities of CE, facilitating needs from practice to match our institutions' capacity for more and better CE, with a special focus on its recognition and rewards (R&R) in academic careers. Spoke-site coordinators will also foster internal embedding of CE activities by **connecting policy advisory bodies and professional support structures with best practices**, for instance, by informing the work of ethics committees with existing examples of community-driven ethical protocols, data-sharing guidelines, and developing inclusive consent formats. (**FA1.2**). To support this, by M24, targeted info-sessions will be co-developed and delivered to train professional support staff on transdisciplinary methodologies, ensuring that workflows reflexively adapt to participatory approaches to align with the underlying normative and practical requirements of CE methodologies. These workflows will include funding acquisition support for CE initiatives, through spoke-site coordinators expertise and advisory roles, also exploring novel practices, such as participatory budgeting models, and civic consultation methods in specialized domains. Alongside leveraging internal communication channels and OS campaigns to raise awareness and promote CE, a key priority will be to **demonstrate and showcase the impact** of CE practices (**F1.3**). By M12, evaluation frameworks and impact assessment tools such as EUR's Evaluating Societal Impact Toolbox, LU's Impact Lab Toolkit, and emergent best practice will be shared as resources but also applied via self-evaluation to showcase impact stories on the HIER website and partner institutions' websites and research support portals. Next to it, the team aims to facilitate the deeper integration of CE into institutional policy and research practices with tangible HR policy uptake. We will also explore the use of seed funding and extend existing awards initiatives to both celebrate achievements and incentivize impactful engaged research.

FA2: Developing CE Capacity & Knowledge Exchange. This focus area equips (early-career) researchers and educators with skills, resources, and networks to foster sustainable CE initiatives. By M6, HIER will **establish a joint community of practice** connecting project partners, researchers, and CE practitioners through peer-led workshops, showcases, and discussion sessions (**F2.1**). This network will bridge both inter- and intra-institutional silos to foster and sustain knowledge-sharing through our Open Science communities and other learning communities. **CE training modules** will be delivered and made widely accessible to early-career researchers and novice CE across the partnership building on the Civic Engagement in Action series (**FA2.2**). By M24, a central online HIER website will provide a **curated selection of high quality CE resources**, toolkits, guides for the HIER network, to be profiled along

with HIER-produced resources on the [CS-NL Knowledge Platform](#) and EU-Citizen.Science Platform for wider dissemination (**FA 2.3**). Tools and lessons learned via initiatives such as EUR's [Design Impact Transition](#) (DIT) platform and LU's [CWTS research institute](#) specialising in monitoring and evaluation will be integrated in the resource list and activated through topical community-sessions, as well as through the earlier mentioned support structures' info-sessions.

FA3: Liaising Collaborations & Network Access. A structured entry point for institutional and civic collaborations and networks will **facilitate new partnerships** and provide researchers and stakeholders with **streamlined access to diverse networks (FA3.1)**. By M12, spoke-site coordinators will have jointly mapped transdisciplinary academic and civic partnerships leveraging strategic alliances' resources. Assisted by HIER's network collaborators, they will connect researchers with (thematic) epistemic communities, as well as local and regional stakeholders, liaising access to the relevant expertise and engagement opportunities. Additionally, HIER will **tackle participation fatigue in over-researched and engaged communities (FA3.2)** with the ambition to promote sustainable regional engagement. Relying on insights from the landscaping exercise of existing projects and partnerships, the team will identify gaps and opportunities of CE research in the region, informing support mechanisms across focus areas and, more specifically, designing annual researcher-dedicated awareness sessions. **Strengthening collaborations with local and regional stakeholders** will facilitate sustainable and equitable relationships within HIER partnership (**FA3.3**). Through iterative engagement during the funding period, the Hub will actively link its activities with academic networks and civic partners, fostering sustained 'community-driven' engagement. For example, regular **cross-programming** with complementary CE initiatives, committing HIER's resources for the success and visibility of civic collaborators (such as WijkWijs, WijkStad, Wijk Universiteit) will facilitate issue-specific exchanges to foster (good practice of) CE and sustain long-term alliances.

Governance and Collaborative Spoke Framework. The HIER collaboration between regional universities and medical centers is enabled by the following governance structure: The **Coordinating Team (CT)** is jointly responsible for strategic direction, monitoring progress, implementation of tasked FA activities and related deliverables across the partnership and related embedding within each spoke-site location. The CT consists of the EUR, TUD, and LU spoke-site coordinators, who will meet by-weekly to align their activities with overall project goals. FA task activities will be distributed reflecting expertise, resources, and spokes-person capacity, ensuring both distributed leadership and cross-collaboration. The **Hub Coordinator** oversees project and financial management, and the data management plan for the Hub, and supports the CT throughout the project, particularly through facilitation of coordinating activities. The **Operating Team (OT)** contributes expertise and leads on related tasks in the implementation of Hub activities, joins mutual learning activities and liaise with their own wider networks. It includes the CT, and the larger team of colleagues named in Section 2.1. The **Stakeholder Board (STB)** ensures that the Hub activities align with stakeholder interests, provides feedback on the implementation of the workplan, and informs the strategic direction of HIER through by-annual meetings. It consists of individuals invited from key stakeholder groups, including an interdisciplinary group from the academic community, network collaborators, and engagement representatives within the partnering institutions (amongst others, Prof. Arwin van Buuren, and Prof. Frank van der Hoeven).

Long-Term Embedding of the Hub. This is secured via the partners' commitment to sustainability and continuity at the core of the HIER vision, ensuring continued operation beyond the project's funding period by focusing on both (a) knowledge co-production and its (b) integration into university structures.

HIER leverages existing staff, resources, and collaborations between the three partner universities, building on ongoing initiatives such as the CE training to demonstrate a shared commitment to CE and lay groundwork for HIER's long-term sustainability. HIER aligns with the strategic priorities of all three partner universities: EUR's vision to further strengthen its profile as an engaged university in its next strategic period; TUD's engagement in the 4TU federation, championing the concept of a 'Fourth Generation University'; and LU's commitment to generating meaningful societal impact via strategic collaborations with public and private partners in our regional ecosystems. By making a tangible contribution to delivering on these priorities, HIER has the key internal stakeholder support to ensure integration into institutional planning and policy development, as also evidenced by HIER team in-kind commitment. The project funding thus serves as a catalyst for enabling the development of support structures and resources within the central support units and operations where the spoke-coordinators' work is currently embedded, respectively, within EUR's [Engagement & Research Services](#), TUD's [Library Open Science Programme](#), and LU's [Citizen Science Lab](#).

3. Existing network and network expansion (criterion 3: 20%)

Aligning with the EU-funded project INCENTIVE's work, **HIER's networked approach** will empower internal and external stakeholders to co-create new knowledge in a transdisciplinary way. HIER activities will be fully embedded in the HIER's network partnership from the start, via thematic and regional CE programmes and initiatives.

The HIER partnership builds on the strong strategic regional alliances of LDE (Leiden-Delft-Erasmus) and its collaborative interdisciplinary research centers and educational programs, and Convergence (EUR, TUD, Erasmus MC) which applies a living lab approach to build a leading regional research and innovation ecosystem. These alliances, with their established connections to municipalities and key civil society representatives, play a critical role in facilitating the proposed institutional dialogues. For example, the LDE Centre for Bold Cities can support reflections around the potential of CE for municipal policy impacts, as highlighted in their white paper. Alliance networks will also be crucial to discuss, define, and align on responsible CE research as well as educational initiatives in the region. For instance, the Convergence Resilient Delta initiative can liaise connections with the Rijnmond-based local networks and civic organizations such as the Afrikaanderwijk Cooperative neighbourhood-based advisory bureau. Academic networks within the LDE Centre Governance of Migration & Diversity and the international LDE Nuvoni Centre for Frugal Innovation can enable inclusive conversations around responsible, transformative, and de-colonizing research practices with, for, and by citizens and communities. Furthermore, HIER can reflect on inclusivity in local contexts of vulnerability and marginalization via the interdisciplinary Health Campus The Hague, a partnership between LUMC, Leiden University and societal stakeholders in HealthCare. Network partner expertise in the fields of inclusivity, international CBPR, and research with medical vulnerabilities will also offer best practices to input HIER's advisory services and capacity-building activities.

Similarly, externally funded research collaborations such as IANUS, focusing on anchoring societal trust in science, and COALESCE's competence centre for science communication, already embedded in the team, and other numerous projects which spoke-site coordinators will contribute mapping, will amplify HIER's knowledge basis. These collaborations can offer guideline and resource contributions to HIER's resource platform for further dissemination and activation through the intended HIER training modules and knowledge-sharing community events. Existing communities of practice with mutually beneficial expertise including Open Science Communities (OSCR, OSCD, OSCL), jointly with other learning communities, such as the LDE Transdisciplinary Education community, and the Resilient Delta Kick Starter community, will further strengthen HIER's capacity building.

Additionally, academic networks like Vital Cities and Citizens (VCC) will facilitate connections with Rotterdam's civil society communities and civic experts to contribute to knowledge sharing and awareness sessions around research fatigue and engagement opportunities in the local area. The network access and liaising function of the Hub relies in many ways on the wider partnership network, and its potential for expansion. Both partnership liaising and advisory services by spoke-coordinators will be supported by 'civic assets' of the HIER's partnership network: For example, the WijkWijs platform, which currently supports ten neighborhood-based initiatives in Rotterdam aiming to transform ways in which academic communities engage with civic epistemic communities, and other locally-based initiatives, such as WijStad, Wijkuniversiteit, and Leren met de Stad in Leiden. Civic network partnerships will be further explored throughout the funding period to strengthen HIER's transdisciplinary dimension and the Hub's potential to create value for citizens and communities in the region.

The preliminary communication plan for the establishment and expansion of HIER partnership network will focus on three key areas: (a) **HIER's partnership-network**, (b) **expansion strategy**, and (c) **activities memory**. Core partnership communications will include regular joint newsletters, shared events, and collaborative environments to foster ongoing engagement and knowledge exchange among partners. The expansion strategy will involve targeted outreach to potential new partners by showcasing HIER's impact through case studies and success stories. Each HIER partner will assess new partners' interest in contributing, joining, and benefiting from HIER's action lines and outputs. Regardless of levels of involvement, all HIER-produced guidance, resources, and tools will be made available to the partnership wider network under a CC-BY-NC 4.0 International (Non-commercial/Attribution) license, supporting communities of practice, resource repositories, and opportunities for mutual learning and knowledge exchange. Last, activities' memory will be maintained through the partner universities' repositories, capturing past and current engagement activities to foster knowledge sharing and continuous improvement. This will be key to the long-term growth of HIER's partnership network and future sustainability beyond the lifetime of the project funding.

4. Impact (criterion 4: 10%)

HIER's FAs and related action lines have been designed to achieve key requirements and entail complex internal and inter-partner collaborations, including external partners and societal actors in existing alliances and future collaborations. Aligning with the [NPOS2030 Ambition Document for Open Science](#), these are (a) **support and training** for researchers and educators to become familiar with skills, knowledge, and methods, (b) **lively networks and communities** of practice for mutual learning, and further development of best practice, and (c) **capacity building** at knowledge institutions to facilitate and support this. It is also crucial that knowledge institutes (d) update their **reward structures** to recognize and value these practices within academic career paths for researchers and the field of practice to flourish and the necessary culture change to take place. We will primarily monitor and evaluate progress on achieving these requirements in terms of **outcomes** and **outputs** that reflect these objectives, with particular attention to the processes and internal support structures put in place, as shown in the below table.

The **expected impacts** in relation to FAs' goals includes (a) **policy change**, ensuring that CE practices are explicitly embedded in internal HR policies and R&R initiatives, reinforcing strong and sustained collaborations between science, society, and governance; (b) **institutional change**, mainstreaming CE practices within research support, funding acquisition, and processes for responsible, open, and ethical engagement in research, so that CE is not only embedded but also actively supported to foster innovation and effectiveness; (c) **excellence**, enhancing research quality and professionalizing CE practices, enabling researchers, educators, and staff practicing CE to flourish in their career paths; and (d) **societal benefits**, strengthening direct and reciprocal access between academic and local communities, ensuring that societal actors are included in systems of knowledge co-production and innovation, and integrating knowledge institutions within the cultural, social, and intellectual fabric of our societies and local areas. The Hub provides the infrastructure and context for collaborating institutions to build capacity for meaningful civic engagement, ensuring that these impacts are realized and sustained.

To **monitor and assess progress** on achieving the requirements of the HIER partnership we will first make use of the 'Reflection and Stock-taking Tools' contained in the [Time4CS project's Monitoring Toolkit](#), which are structured around the four intervention areas of (i) participatory research practices and impact assessment, (ii) CE education and awareness, (iii) CE support resources and infrastructure, and (iv) internal HR policy and career assessment. This will serve as our 'grounding actions' to jointly define our vision, success criteria, plan for the inclusion of key internal and external (societal) stakeholders, further develop HIER's workplan and timeline with identified task leads, that also will describe known and anticipated obstacles, and required resources. This work will lead to the co-development of **HIER evaluation framework** as a living document that builds on the 'Time4CS indicators' for institutional change in knowledge institutes, the INCENTIVE project's 'Indicator Set' for monitoring the progress toward their own CS Hub objectives, and CWTS' monitoring and evaluation frameworks for RRI. The team will thus adapt these to the specific needs, objectives, and success criteria of the HIER partners, following the 'Co-Act project's 6 Principles for Co-Evaluation', namely responsible planning, participant ownership, inclusivity and responsiveness, flexibility and reflexivity, openness and transparency, and transformative perspective.